

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10278891

13

EVALUATION OF BREAST LESIONS BY FINE NEEDLE ASPIRATION CYTOLOGY AND CORRELATION WITH HISTOPATHOLOGICAL EXAMINATION

Authors:

Dr Hiral Chauhan (Senior Resident), Dr. Alpa Patel (Tutor), Dr. Nanda Jagrit (Associate Professor), Dr. Krutina Parikh (1st year Resident), Dr. Shubham Panchal (1st year Resident), Dr. Maulik Patel, Pathology department, AMC MET medical college, Maninagar, Ahmedabad.

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Nanda Jagrit

Mobile number: 9824485426

Email id: jagritnanda34@gmail.com

Address: Pathology department, AMC MET medical college, Maninagar, Ahmedabad.

ABSTRACT:

INTRODUCTION: Breast cancer is the most common cancer in worldwide between age of 20-59 years' females. It is responsible for 15% of total deaths due to cancers. FNAC is one of the important components of 'triple approach', which has been widely accepted for the preoperative diagnosis of breast lesions.

AIM: To establish utility and effectiveness in diagnosis of breast lesion by FNAC and find the incidence of breast cancer in palpable lump in different age groups.

MATERIAL AND METHODS: In this study 100 cases of breast lump referred by the Surgery Department of LG Hospital was included in study period

from August 2016 to October 2018. **RESULT:** Out of the 100 cases, in 99 cases the aspirates were adequate for interpretation. Out of 100, 90 cases underwent a biopsy and could be correlated histopathologically. According to NBSBSP, there was 1 case in C1 category, 64 cases in C2 category, 3 cases in C3 category, 2 cases in C4 category and 30 cases in C5 category.

CONCLUSION: The present study categorized by NBSBSP criteria conclude 100% confirmation in C4 and C5 category in age group above 40 years showing malignancy by histopathology. The overall sensitivity in the study was 83.33%, specificity was 100%, positive predictive value in disease was 100% and the false negative percentage was 16.66%. FNAC is an accurate and reliable preoperative diagnostic tool for breast lesions.

Keyword: Breast Lesions, Aspiration Cytology, histopathological, correlation

INTRODUCTION:

Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) is a technique which is routinely done on palpable lesions such as superficial growths of the skin, sub cutis, soft tissues and organs such as thyroid, breast, salivary glands, and superficial lymph nodes. Modern imaging techniques like USG and CT applied to organs and deep-seated lesions help in obtaining material through transthoracic and trans peritoneal approaches.¹

Breast cancer is the most common cancer in women worldwide and it is the leading cause of cancer death for women between ages 20 to 59 years. It is responsible for 26% of new cancer diagnosis in females and it is responsible for 15% of the cancer related deaths in women.

FNAC is one of the important components of 'triple approach', which has been widely accepted for the preoperative diagnosis of breast lesions.² Most cases of breast lumps are benign³, but

sometimes, it is difficult to determine whether a suspicious lump is benign or malignant, simply by doing a clinical examination. FNAC can reduce the number of open breast biopsies.⁴ The advantages are - it provides rapid and accurate diagnosis, is diagnostic as well as therapeutic in cystic conditions, and permits a number of ancillary studies such as hormone receptor analysis, flow cytometry, and molecular diagnostic studies⁵. Thus, it plays a major role as an important preoperative assessment procedure along with clinical correlation and imaging which are referred to as the "Triple test."⁶The limitation of a FNAC is its inability to separate in situ and invasive carcinoma.⁷

The overall accuracy of FNAC in diagnosis of breast lesions is reported to be about 97.40%. The diagnostic sensitivity, specificity, and predictive value of a positive result of FNAC for diagnosing breast lesions are 93.80%, 98.21%, and 92.70% respectively.⁸

MATERIALS&METHOD:

- All indoor and outdoor patients having breast lump referred by department of surgery, LG Hospital from August 2016 to October 2018.
- Study conducted in Department of Pathology, AMC MET Medical College, L.G. Hospital, Maninagar, Ahmedabad.
- The procedure was explained to the patient and written consent obtained; then patient underwent for FNAC as per standard guideline.
- The slides were fixed in 95% methyl alcohol and stained with H & E / PAP stains. A few air-dried smears were taken for the Giemsa stain.
- Histopathology: Biopsy and specimen received in histopathology section of AMC MET Medical College & LG Hospital were processed and evaluated by H & E stain.

RESULTS:

The present study includes FNAC material from the 100 cases of breast lesions from August 2016 to October 2018 at the Department of Pathology AMC MET Medical College & LG Hospital.

Out of the 100 cases, in 99 cases the aspirates were adequate for interpretation and out of them 62 were moderately cellular, and 33 were highly cellular. Only 90 cases underwent a biopsy and could be correlated histo-pathologically. The observations of the study were as follows:

AGE AND SEX DISTRIBUTION: The age of the patients ranged from 11 to 80 years. There were 93 female patients and 7 male patients. The age distribution in relation to sex was shown in Table 1. Majority of the patients were between 21-40 years.

Table-1 Age and Sex distribution

Age in year	<=20	21- 40	41- 60	61- 80	Total
Males	2	2	1	2	7
Females	16	43	25	9	93
Total	18	45	26	11	100

Chart -1 Age and Sex distribution

Out of 100 cases, in 51 cases the lesion was located in the right breast and in 40 cases located in the left breast and in 09 cases, bilateral lesions were observed.

The mass was located in the upper outer quadrant in 62 cases, in the upper inner quadrant in 13 cases and in the lower outer quadrant in 5 cases of breast swelling. It was located in the lower inner quadrant in 2 cases and in the sub areolar quadrant in 18 cases. The mass involved both the upper outer and inner quadrants in 4 cases and was located in both the lower outer and inner quadrants in 1 case.

NHSBSP REPORTING CRITERIA OF FNAC OF BREAST LESIONS:

According to NHSBSP, the cytology of 100 cases were analyzed and categorized into 5 categories from C1 to C5. There was 1 case in C1 category, 64 cases in C2 category, 3 cases in C3 category, 2 cases in C4 category and 30 cases in C5 category.

Table 2- Cytology result categorization

Category	No. of Cases	Characteristic
C1	01	Inadequate
C2	64	Benign
C3	03	Atypia, probably benign
C4	02	Suspicious for malignancy
C5	30	Malignancy

C1: CATEGORY LESIONS: Single case of inadequate smear was observed. The mass was located in the right breast in the central quadrant. The smear was inadequate for interpretation.

C2: CATEGORY-BENIGN LESIONS: In this category 64 benign cases included, out of them 7 cases were reported as an inflammatory lesion. A cytological diagnosis of breast abscess was made in these 3 cases. 2 cases were diagnosed as granulomatous mastitis and another 2 cases were diagnosed as an acute mastitis. All these cases were confirmed histologically. In this 2 category Fibroadenoma was the most common lesion found in 23 cases. Surgery was performed in 20 cases and the diagnosis of Fibroadenoma was confirmed by histopathology in all 20 cases.

3 cases in female presented with a mass in the breast diagnosed as Phyllodes tumor. The smear showed moderate cellularity with groups of spindle cells, occasional giant cells and few ductal cells in a hemorrhagic background. All 3 cases were confirmed histologically.

Fig.1-Bimodal population of cells showing ductal epithelial and myoepithelial cells in fibrous stroma-fibroadenoma.H&Ex40

Fig-2 Histopathology of fibroadenoma-(pericanalicular pattern). H&Ex40

Fig-3 Low power view of phyllodes tumor. The increased stromal cellularity. H&E x 10

22 cases were diagnosed at cytology as benign proliferative breast disease. Surgery was performed in 16 cases and the diagnosis of benign proliferative breast disease was confirmed by histopathology in all 16 cases.

There was a case of 35years old female presented with sub areolar region swelling diagnosed as fibrocystic breast disease and confirmed histologically.

7 cases were diagnosed as gynecomastia at cytology in the male breast. Out of them 6 cases confirmed histologically and one case showed intracystic papillary carcinoma of breast. **C3 CATEGORY:** A C3 category diagnosis of atypia, probably benign at cytology was given on 3 cases out of which Cytology showed atypical ductal epithelial hyperplasia (probably benign) was given in 3 cases. Based on this, the patients underwent excision of the mass and the histopathology showed infiltrating ductal carcinoma (NOS type), infiltrating ductal carcinoma-mucin secreting type and ductal carcinoma in situ.

C4 CATEGORY: A C4 category diagnosis of suspicious of malignancy at cytology was given on 2 cases. The cytology showed cellular smears were loosely cohesive sheets and clusters of ductal epithelial cells having large, pleomorphic, hyperchromatic nuclei. Mitosis was seen. Based on this, the patients underwent excision of the mass and the histopathology showed infiltrating ductal carcinoma (NOS type) in all the cases.

C5 CATEGORY: Out of the 30 malignant cases, 29 was reported in cytology as ductal carcinoma. The smears were moderately to highly cellular with pleomorphic malignant ductal epithelial cells in loose clusters, sheets, and in singly. All 30 cases were confirmed histologically.

Fig.18 Carcinoma cell groups showing pleomorphism of the nuclei with hyperchromatism and clumped chromatin. Giemsa x40

Fig-19 Histopathology of an IDC with tubule formation. H&E x40

Out of 100 cases, 90 had a corresponding histopathological diagnosis. With this confirmation an overall sensitivity, specificity, predictive value of a positive result and percentage of false negative indices were calculated in Table 3.

Out of 90 biopsies done, the discrepancies at cytology were as follows:

-Out of 90 cases biopsied, 30 cases diagnosed as malignant at cytology proved to be malignant at histology also. Therefore, the FNAC proved to be 100 % sensitive and specific in the diagnosis of malignant lesion in our study.

-Single case diagnosed as Paget's disease of breast with underlying infiltrating ductal carcinoma at histology was reported as an inadequate aspirate at cytology.

-Single case diagnosed as intracystic papillary carcinoma and its cytology was reported as a benign cystic breast lesion possibility of gynecomastia at cytology. (False negative diagnosis in disease)

-Out of three cases in C5 category, 2 cases diagnosed as infiltrating ductal carcinoma and 1 case diagnosed as ductal carcinoma in situ at histology were reported as ductal epithelial hyperplasia with atypia at cytology. (False negative diagnosis in disease)

-Two case diagnosed as infiltrating ductal carcinoma at histology were reported as suspicious of malignancy at cytology. (False negative diagnosis in disease)

True Positive (TP)=30, True Negative (TN)=53, False Negative (FN)=6, False Positive (FP)=0

Table 3-Overall Statistical Analysis

Test	Formula	Percentage
Sensitivity	$TP (30)/TP (30) +FN (6) \times 100$	83.33%
Specificity	$TN (53)/FP (0) +TN (53) \times 100$	100%
Positive predictive value	$TP (30)/TP (30) +FP (0) \times 100$	100%
False negative percentage	$FN (6)/TP (30) +FN (6) \times 100$	16.66%

DISCUSSION:

Present study included the FNAC material of 100 breast cases in which the cytomorphological features were studied in detail. The age of the patients ranged up to 80 years with the majority in the 21-40-year age group. Out of 100 cases, majority of the breast masses were located in the right breast in the upper outer quadrant and least in the lower outer & inner quadrant.

Out of 100 cases, in 99 cases the aspirates were adequate and 1 was inadequate for interpretation.

TABLE:4 COMPARISON OF VARIOUS AGE GROUP INCIDENCE OF BENIGN AND MALIGNANT BREAST LESIONS WITH OTHER STUDIES

Age (Year)	Present study		Dr. Venu Anand et al. 201711		Neena Chauhan et al. 201212	
	Benign	Malignant	Benign	Malignant	Benign	Malignant
<= 20	18(28.12%)	0(0.00%)	23(16.31%)	0(0.00%)	12(14.63%)	0(0.00%)
21-40	36(56.25%)	6(20.0%)	93(65.95%)	8(19.91%)	55(67.07%)	33(36.36%)
41-60	8 (12.5%)	17(56.67%)	23(16.31%)	27(65.85%)	13(15.85%)	42(46.15%)
61-80	2 (3.12%)	7(23.33%)	02 (1.41%)	6(14.63%)	2(2.43%)	16(17.58%)
Total	64(100%)	30(100%)	141(100%)	41(100%)	82(100%)	91(100%)

TABLE: 5 COMPARISONS OF CYTOLOGICAL BENIGN LESION AND HISTOPATHOLOGY WITH OTHER STUDIES

Studies	Histopathological diagnosis

	No. of cytological benign lesion (total) (C2)	Benign	Malignant
ZhangQin et al. ⁹	215	213(99.07%)	02(0.93%)
A. Z. Mohammed et al. ¹⁰	61	58(95.08%)	03(4.92%)
Present study	54	53 (98.15%)	01 (1.85%)

TABLE: 6 COMPARISONS OF CYTOLOGICALLY SUSPICIOUS LESION AND HISTOPATHOLOGY WITH OTHER STUDIES

Studies	No. of cytologically suspicious lesion (total) (C4)	Histopathological diagnosis	
		Malignant	Benign
Zhang Qin et al. ⁹	28	26(92.86%)	02 (7.14%)
A. Z. Mohammed et al. ¹⁰	02	02(100%)	00(0.00%)
Present study	02	02 (100%)	00 (0.00%)

TABLE: 7 COMPARISONS OF CYTOLOGICAL MALIGNANT LESION AND HISTOPATHOLOGY WITH OTHER STUDIES

Studies	No. of cytological malignant lesion (total) (C5)	Histopathological diagnosis (Malignant lesion)
ZhangQin et al. ⁹	73	73(100%)
A. Z. Mohammed et al. ¹⁰	27	27(100%)
Present study	30	30 (100%)

Single case diagnosed as Paget's disease of breast with underlying infiltrating ductal carcinoma at histology was reported as an inadequate aspirate at cytology.

In C3 category, we have 3 cases of ductal epithelial hyperplasia (probably benign) underwent excision of mass and confirmed histologically.

TABLE: 8 COMPARISONS OF SENSITIVITY AND SPECIFICITY OF PRESENT STUDY WITH OTHER STUDIES

Studies	Sensitivity	Specificity
ZhangQin et al. ⁹	97.1%	97.3%

A.Z. Mohammed et al . ¹⁰	90.5%	100%
Present study	83.33%	100%

As shown in all tables our results are comparable with other studies.

CONCLUSION:

FNAC is an accurate, inexpensive, safe, repeatable and rapid diagnostic procedure that has been applicable in the evaluation of breast lesion in any patient. It offers the advantage of rapid diagnosis with minimum surgical intervention; and it may help the surgeon in pre-operative planning. Our study concluded that FNAC is highly sensitive and specific diagnostic procedure for breast mass lesion.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Orell SR, Sterret GF, Whitaker D. Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology, 4th edition, Churchill Livingstone: Elsevier, 2005: 2(a); 165-166(b); 176-201(c).
- Kocjan G, Bourgain C, Fassina A, et al. The role of breast FNAC in diagnosis & clinical management: a survey of current practice. *Cytopathology*. 2008; 19:271-78.
- Cochrane RA, Singhal H, Mony penny IJ, Sebster DJ, Lyons K, Manse IRE. Evaluation of general practitioner referrals to a specialist breast clinic according to the UK national guidelines. *EuroJSurgOncol*. 1997;23(3):198-201.
- Hindle WH, Payne PA, Pan EY. The use of fine needle aspiration in the evaluation of persistent palpable dominant breast masses. *Am J Obstetrics Gynaecol*. 1993;168 (6 Part1): 1814—18.
- Bibbo M, Wilbur DC. *Comprehensive Cytopathology*, 3rd edition, Philadelphia: Saunders Elsevier, 2008: 713-715(a); 725-750(b)
- Mudde Gowda PH, Linge Gowda JB, Kurpad R, Konapur PG, Shivarudrappa AS, Subramaniam PM. The value of system at ic pattern analysis in FNAC of breast lesions: 225 cases with cytohistological correlation. *Journal of Cytology* 2011;28 (1):13-18.
- Bilous M. Breast core needle biopsy: Issues and controversies. *Modern Pathology* 2010; 23:536-545.
- Rocha PD, Nadkarni NS, Menezes S. Fine needle aspiration biopsy of breast lesions and histopathological correlation. *Acta Cytol* 1997;41(3):705-712.
- Zhang Qin, Nie Shigui, Chen Yuhua, Zhou Limei. Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology of Breast Lesions: Analysis of 323 Cases. *The Chinese-German Journal of Clinical Oncology* 2004;3(3):172-74.
- Mohammad AZ, Edino ST, Ochicha O, Alhassan SU. Value of fine needle aspiration biopsy in pre-operative diagnosis of palpable breast lumps in resource-poor countries: a Nigerian experience. *Annals of African Medicine*. 2005;4(1):19-22.
- Dr Venu Anand Dr S. selvi, Dr. C. Sofiya, Dr. V. Ramya. A study of aspiration cytology of breast and histopathological correlation. *IOSR Journal of dental and medical science*. 2279-0853, volume 16, Issue 12 Ver, XII (Dec.2017), pp-58-61.
- Neena Chauhan, V.P. Pathak, Meena Harsh, Sunis Saini. Cyto histopathological correlation in palpable breast lesions: Analysis of 200 cases. *Indian Medical Gazette*-December 2012, 473-478.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST: Nil

FUNDING: Nil

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT: Nil